

Monitoring of human enteric virus and coliphages throughout water reuse system of wastewater treatment plants to irrigation endpoint of leafy greens

Pilar Truchado ^{a,*}, Alberto Garre ^b, Maria I. Gil ^a, Pedro J. Simón-Andreu ^c, Gloria Sánchez ^d, Ana Allende ^a

^a Research Group on Quality and Safety of Fruits and Vegetables, Department of Food Science and Technology, CEBAS-CSIC, Campus Universitario de Espinardo, 25, 30100 Murcia, Spain

^b Food Microbiology, Wageningen University & Research, P.O. Box 17, 6700 AA Wageningen, the Netherlands

^c Entidad Regional de Saneamiento y Depuración de Murcia (ESAMUR), Avda. Juan Carlos I, s/n. Ed. Torre Jemeca, 30009 Murcia, Spain

^d Department of Preservation and Food Safety Technologies, Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology, IATA-CSIC, Av. Agustín Escardino 7, Paterna 46980, Valencia, Spain

HIGHLIGHTS

- The fate of human viruses and coliphages in two water reuse systems was assayed.
- Prevalence of HAV was low, linked to sewage, while non-positive HAV plant samples.
- Reclamation treatments reduce norovirus and coliphages in reclaimed water.
- Coliphages reductions were below the limit established by the European Regulation.
- Norovirus was only detected in 6% of leafy green samples.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 20 October 2020

Received in revised form 25 March 2021

Accepted 25 March 2021

Available online 30 March 2021

Editor: Ewa Korzeniewska

Keywords:

Reclaimed water

Water scarcity

Human norovirus

Hepatitis A

Coliphages

Agricultural water

ABSTRACT

One solution to current water scarcity is the reuse of treated wastewater. Water reuse systems have to be examined as a whole, including the efficacy of water-reclamation treatments and the operation steps from the wastewater inlet into the WWTP to the irrigation endpoint, including the irrigated crop. In this study, the monitoring of human enteric viruses and coliphages were assessed in two water reused systems. The presence of hepatitis A virus (HAV) and human noroviruses genogroups I and II (GI and GII) were analyzed by real-time RT-PCR (RT-qPCR) in water ($n = 475$) and leafy green samples ($n = 95$). Total coliphages were analyzed by the double-layer agar plaque technique. The prevalence of HAV in water samples was very low (c.a. 2%), mostly linked to raw sewage, while for leafy green samples, none was positive for HAV. In leafy greens, prevalence of norovirus was low (less than 5–6%). The highest reductions for norovirus were observed in samples taken from the water reservoirs used by the growers near the growing field. The virus die-off during water storage due to solar radiation could be considered as an additional improvement. Reclamation treatments significantly reduced the prevalence and the counts of noroviruses GI and GII and coliphages in reclaimed water. However, the coliphage reductions (c.a. 5 log) do not comply with the specifications included in the new European regulation on reclaimed water (≥ 6.0 log). Correlations between noroviruses GI and GII and coliphages were found only in positive samples with high concentrations (>4.5 log PFU/100 mL). A high percentage of samples (20–25%) negative for total coliphages showed moderate norovirus counts (1–3 logs), indicating that coliphages are not the most suitable indicator for the possible presence of human enteric viruses.

© 2021 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: p.truchado@cebas.csic.es (P. Truchado).

1. Introduction

Water is a limited source, particularly for Mediterranean countries that are presently experiencing water scarcity which will be aggravated by the expected increasing water demand during the coming years and climate change (Mancuso et al., 2020). International governmental organizations respond to the increased pressures on water resources by limiting extraction from surface water and groundwater bodies, reducing the discharge of treated wastewater into water bodies, and promoting water savings through multiple uses for urban wastewater (EC, 2020). Additionally, the reuse of treated wastewater as agricultural water should be facilitated if any potential health and environmental risks are avoided, mostly food safety risks associated with the irrigated products (Tombini Decol et al., 2019). Special precautions must be achieved on fresh produce with high contact with irrigation water, such as leafy greens. Reclaimed water is defined as wastewater that has gone through at least secondary treatment. Based on the recently published European Union legislation, health standards can be achieved if quality requirements for reclaimed water intended for agricultural irrigation are established and fulfilled by all the actors participating in the water reuse system (EC, 2020).

Human enteric viruses such as human noroviruses and Hepatitis A virus (HAV) are identified as causative agents of foodborne disease outbreaks associated with fruits and vegetables (Pearce-Walker et al., 2020). A previous study already reported the potential risk of crop contamination by noroviruses when reclaimed water was used for irrigation (López-Gálvez et al., 2016). However, the lack of monitoring for the presence of viruses in irrigation water prevents the comprehensive understanding of their impact on public health (Pearce-Walker et al., 2020; Hedberg and Osterholm, 1993). Recently, more information about the significance of viral pathogens in irrigation waters is available, particularly evidence related to reclaimed water.

Specific focus has received the identification of an appropriate indicator microorganism, which could be correlated with the presence or absence of harmful viral species (Pearce-Walker et al., 2020; Chacón et al., 2020; Boehm, 2019).

Identification and quantification of human enteric viruses are costly and time-consuming. This fact lead, to the search for microbial indicators to characterize viral contamination and the validation. of reclamation treatments (McMinn et al., 2017; Ji et al., 2020). Fecal indicator bacteria, particularly *Escherichia coli*, are commonly used for assessing the microbial quality of wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) outlets. Worldwide regulations and guidelines for agricultural water reuse are mainly human-health centered. In most cases, water quality parameters are based on *E. coli* concentrations (Shoushtarian and Negahban-Azar, 2020; EC, 2020). However, many studies have already demonstrated that a bacterial indicator like *E. coli* may not accurately represent the spectrum of pathogens present in feces, particularly human enteric viruses (Pearce-Walker et al., 2020). More research is needed to understand the dynamics of pathogenic viruses and microbial indicators at the urban wastewater treatment plant and throughout the entire water reuse system, from the entry of WWTP to the point of use. The objective of the present study was to assess the prevalence and concentration of pathogenic viruses, including human noroviruses and HAV throughout the water reuse system and the establishment of correlations between human enteric viruses and coliphages.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Site description

Two water reuse systems were included in the current study. WWTPs consisted of a series of sections or operation steps: a primary filtration treatment where the filter removed larger objects and particles. After that, a secondary treatment, including coagulation-flocculation and complementary lamellar clarification. This step was

followed by filtration on an open sand bed filter and then a disinfection treatment as tertiary treatment. The selection of the experimental settings was based on two criteria: 1) the disinfection treatment after the secondary treatment and 2) the proximity of the WWTPs to commercial growing fields, which favoured the use of reclaimed water as irrigation water by the local growers. Based on these premises, two WWTPs, one using ultraviolet-C (UV-C) light and another using sodium hypochlorite (Chlorine) as tertiary treatments, were selected. These two WWTPs were located only a few kilometers from commercial growing fields that used reclaimed water as the main water source for irrigation. The two water reuse systems were fully characterized including water reservoirs, canals and irrigation pipes. One WWTP was located in Lorca (37°30' 13,86"N, 1° 41' 38,07"W), Murcia (Spain) using chlorine as tertiary treatment (WWTP 1). The other one located in Cartagena, Murcia (Spain) (37° 44' 51,81"N, 0° 59' 12,02"W), equipped with UV-C light as the disinfection treatment (WWTP 2). Fig. 1 shows the schemes of the two water reuse systems selected for this study. The physicochemical characteristics of the outlet water samples (pH and conductivity) were measured using a portable system (Hach, Loveland, Colorado, USA) as previously described Tudela et al., 2019. Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) and Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) were determined by the standard photometric method using the Spectroquant Nova 60 photometer (Merk, Darmstadt, Germany). Culture enumeration of *E. coli* was performed as previously described in Castro-Ibáñez et al. (2015). Climatic data were obtained from the nearby climatic station: Pozo de la Higuera weather station (37° 35' 25,7"N, 1° 43' 32"W) for WWTP 1 and Cartagena (37° 44' 51,81"N, 0° 59' 12,02"W) for WWTP 2, using the local climatological database (SIAM, 2019). Data as the mean of the daily values of temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), and solar radiation (W/m²) during the growing cycles of the crops are included in Table 1

2.2. Sample collection

A total of 475 water and 95 leafy green samples were collected along with the seven growing cycles of leafy greens cultivations (Table 1). Water samples were collected in 5 different locations, including the inlet of the WWTP (inlet), the outlet after the tertiary treatment (outlet) the water reservoir placed at the WWTP (WWTP reservoir), the water reservoir at the growing field (Grower reservoir), and irrigation system (Fig. 2). Crops were grown in commercial fields and included lettuce and baby spinach. Lettuce heads were irrigated using furrow or drip irrigation, while baby spinach was irrigated using overhead irrigation. Water samples and leafy greens were sampled three or four times per trial. Sampling days were along the growing cycle from the day the leafy greens reached the minimum size for sampling until commercial maturity. On each sampling day, five water samples were collected at each sampling point (Fig. 2). Water samples (2 L each) were taken using sterile plastic bottles. Samples of the outlet water of the chlorine tertiary treated (WWTP 1) were neutralized using sodium thiosulphate (50 mg/L) to quench the residual chlorine. Five samples of leafy greens were also taken at each sampling field and time. Samples (100 g each) were randomly following a zig-zag pattern to cover the entire growing area. Leafy green samples were hand-harvested using scissors and stored in sterile plastic bags. Scissors were wiped with ethanol (70%) between samples. All samples were transported under refrigerated conditions in polystyrene boxes to the CEBAS-CSIC laboratory (Murcia, Spain) (40 km max) and stored at 4 °C. All the samples were processed after collection no later than 4 h.

2.3. Sample concentration

Mengovirus (MgV) (6 log PCR/L) was added as a process control virus in all samples to monitor extraction efficiency following the ISO 15216:2019 guidelines. Wastewater inlet samples were concentrated as previously described by Rodríguez-Díaz et al. (2009). Briefly, 30 mL

Fig. 1. Location of the water reuse systems included in this study, indicating the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP 1 and WWTP 2) and the growing fields.

of inlet water was centrifuged at $140,000 \times g$ for 2 h 30 min at 4°C . Then, the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was re-suspended with 5 mL of 0.25 N glycine buffer (pH 9.5) and incubated on ice for 30 min. The solution was neutralized by adding 5 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH = 7). After that, the suspended solids were removed by centrifugation ($12,000 \times g$ for 15 min), and the pellet was again centrifuged at $229,600 \times g$ for 1 h at 4°C . This supernatant was removed and the pellet was re-suspended in 1 mL of PBS. Water samples from the outlet, the WWTP reservoir, the grower reservoir and the irrigation points were concentrated by aluminium hydroxide adsorption-precipitation (APHA, 1989; Randazzo et al., 2019). Two hundred milliliter of water were mixed with 2 mL of 0.9 N AlCl_3 (pH = 3.8), and the pH adjusted to 6 with 1 N NaOH. After mixing slowly at 150 rpm for 15 min at room temperature, the floc was sedimented by centrifugation at $1700 \times g$ for 20 min. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet resuspended in 3 mL of 3% beef extract at pH 7.4 and centrifuged again at $1900 \times g$ for 30 min. The supernatant was decanted and the pellet was re-suspended with 3 mL of sterile PBS. The concentrated samples were kept at -80°C until processing for nucleic acid extraction.

Leafy green tissue samples were concentrated as previously described by ISO/TS 15216-1:2013 and López-Gálvez et al. (2016) with some modifications. Briefly, 25 g were mixed with 40 mL of Tris-glycine buffer (TGBE) at pH 9.5 in a sterile plastic bag with a lateral filter. Then, they were subsequently incubated for 20 min at room

temperature with constant rocking agitation. The mixture was taken from the filter side to remove particulate debris, and the resulting filtrate was centrifuged at $8500 \times g$ 30 min at 4°C to pellet the particles. The resulting supernatant was decanted in a clean tube and the pH adjusted to 7.2 with 5 N HCl. Eluted viruses were concentrated by polyethylene glycol (PEG) (6000, Acros Organics, Geel, Belgium) precipitation. PEG and NaCl were added to obtain a final concentration of 10% w/v PEG and 0.3 M NaCl. Eluate was then incubated with rocking (80 rpm) at 4°C overnight. After that, the eluate was centrifuged at $8500 \times g$ for 30 min at 4°C . The supernatant was discarded and centrifuged again at $8500 \times g$ for another 5 min at 4°C to consolidate the pellet. The supernatant was discarded and pellet was re-suspended in 1 mL of PBS. Samples were stored at -70°C until analysis.

2.4. Coliphage quantification

Levels of total coliphages, simultaneous detection of somatic and F+ coliphages, were quantified by the double-layer agar plaque assay technique using the host strain *E. coli* CB390 (Spanish Type Culture Collection; CECT 9198) (Guzmán et al., 2008) with some modifications. Briefly, *E. coli* CB390 was grown in Luria Bertani Broth (LB, Scharlau, Barcelona, Spain) supplemented with ampicillin ($100 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) at 37°C until the log phase (optical density, OD = 0.3). For coliphage quantification, all water and leafy green samples were processed as described before for sample concentration. One milliliter per concentrate per water samples and $500 \mu\text{L}$ per tissue samples were treated with (10%) of chloroform to disrupt all the bacteria cells and to release the phages. In the case of the inlet samples, ten-fold dilution of each concentrate was performed in SM buffer (5.8 g NaCl, 2.0 g $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 50 mL 1 M Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 2% gelatin in 1 L dH₂O) before treated with chloroform. All the treated samples were centrifuged at $2500 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C and the supernatant was filtered ($0.45 \mu\text{m}$) to remove the presence of any bacteria. For the lower and upper layers in the double agar test, tryptone-yeast-extract glucose (TYG) agar and TYG semisolid agar were supplemented with ampicillin ($100 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and calcium glucose solution according to ISO 10705-1. Tryptone-yeast-extract glucose semisolid agar ($4800 \mu\text{L}$) was supplemented with ampicillin ($100 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$),

Table 1

Quality requirements in the effluent water from the wastewater treatment plants included in the study (WWTP 1 and WWTP 2). Values are the mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 475$) along the growing cycle.

	Lorca	Cartagena
pH	8.2 ± 0.9	7.9 ± 1.5
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	2577 ± 483	2010 ± 440
COD (mg/L)	51.4 ± 10.8	23.8 ± 5.1
BOD5 (mg/L)	4.3 ± 3.1	2.6 ± 0.9
<i>E. coli</i> cfu/100 mL	7.4 ± 0.5	7.8 ± 0.5
TSS	10.0 ± 5.8	4.3 ± 3.1

EC: electrical conductivity; COD: chemical oxygen demand; BOD5: biochemical oxygen demand; TSS: total suspended solids

Fig. 2. Sampling points taken throughout the water reuse systems of wastewater treatment plants to the endpoint of use for irrigation of leafy greens.

calcium glucose solution (50 μL) 100 μL of each supernatant and 100 μL of *E. coli* 390 in the log phase ($\text{OD} = 0.3$). Plates were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h and the levels of total coliphages were expressed in plaque forming units per 100 mL (PFU/100 mL).

2.5. Viral RNA extraction and RT-qPCR quantification

RNA was extracted using the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions with some modifications. Briefly, 140 μL of each water or leafy green tissue concentrated samples were mixed with 25 μL Plant RNA Isolation Aid (Ambion) and 600 μL of lysis buffer from the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit (Randazzo et al., 2019). The homogenate was centrifuged for 5 min at $10,000 \times g$ to remove the debris. The supernatant was heated at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min to lyse the RNA viruses and subsequently processed according to the manufacturer's instructions. After that, RNA was re-suspended in 60 μL of elution buffer from the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit. Real-time RT-PCR (RT-qPCR) was used for enteric virus detection using an ABI 7500 Sequence Detection System (ABI, Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain). Amplification and detection were performed in 96-well plates using RNA Ultrasense One-step Quantitative RT-PCR system (Invitrogen, Waltham, USA). Each reaction was run in duplicate containing 2.5 μL of RNA template. Final concentrations of primers, probe and the applied cycling parameters are listed in Table 3, as suggested by ISO 15216:2019 guidelines. In all cases, a non-template control (NTC) was included using 2.5 μL of RNase-free H_2O instead of the RNA template. Standard curves were made using known concentrations of RNA isolated from human Norovirus GI, GII and HAV kindly provided by Dra. Gloria Sanchez, IATA-CSIC, Valencia, Spain. The limit of detection (LOD) for Norovirus GI, GII, HAV and MgV was determined to be 0.1, 0.13, 0.35 and 0.82 gc per reaction with quantification cycle (Cq) values of 38.38 ± 0.43 , 38.12 ± 0.24 , 36.50 ± 0.35 and 39.75 ± 0.071 , respectively. In the water samples, the theoretical quantification limits of the overall method resulted in 0.8, 1.2, 1.6 and 2.0 log gc/100 mL for Norovirus GI, GII, HAV and mengovirus respectively. In the tissue samples, the theoretical limits of the overall method resulted in 0.3, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.7 log 10 gc/g. Mengovirus recovery rates were calculated and used as quality assurance parameters according to ISO 15216-1:2017. The concentration methods were tested by spiking the samples with MgV. On average, MgV was recovered at ranges of $9.8 \pm 9.3\%$ in the inlet $28.7 \pm 18.9\%$ in the outlet, $26.5 \pm 17.8\%$ in WWTP reservoir, $23.5 \pm 15.8\%$ in the grower reservoir, $20.5 \pm 16.6\%$ in the irrigation point and $10.4 \pm 8.4\%$ in the leafy green samples. In all cases, the internal mengovirus control showed recovery rates $>1\%$, which conformed to ISO15216-2:2017. Additionally, undiluted and ten-fold diluted MgV RNA was tested to check for RT-qPCR inhibitors.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Non-zero microbial loads of norovirus were log-transformed (base-10) and stored along with zero counts (for samples with undetected contamination) in an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel, 2010). For calculation and graphical presentation of the median and interquartile range (IQR) of microbial counts only positive samples (i.e., with numbers above the detection limit) were included. IBM SPSS Statistics 25 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA) and R version 3.5.3 (R Core Team, 2016) were used for statistical analyses. Before the statistical analyses, the test for normality (Shapiro-Wilk) was performed ($P > 0.05$). Given that all data showed normal distribution, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to establish whether there were statistically significant differences among the different samples ($P \leq 0.05$) and then the Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test was applied for multiple comparisons. Each group was indicated by different letters (a, b, c). Except when stated otherwise, P values ≤ 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Correlation between the count of coliphages and the norovirus GI and GII was evaluated using Pearson's correlation with a confidence interval set established at 95%, excluding data points with zero values.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Monitoring of pathogenic virus in water reuse systems

Data related to physicochemical characteristics of the outlet water samples from each WWTP are shown in Table 2. Only 12 out of 570 samples were positive for HAV ten of which corresponded to the inlet and two to the outlet. None of the leafy green samples were positive for HAV. These results agree with previous studies worldwide that reported the absence or the very low prevalence of HAV in sewage, reclaimed water and surface water (Farkas et al., 2018; Rodriguez-Manzano et al., 2010).

Prevalence and levels of noroviruses GI and GII in water and leafy greens samples are summarized in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. All the samples from the inlet of the WWTPs were positive for the presence of noroviruses GI and GII, showing median levels of 3.9 log gc/100 mL (IQR 3.7–4.0) and 4.7 log gc/100 mL (IQR 4.57–4.8), respectively. High percentages (95–100%) of positive inlet samples for norovirus and similar concentrations have already been reported in raw sewage (Randazzo et al., 2019; Eftim et al., 2017; Campos et al., 2016; Hata et al., 2011). Reclamation treatments in WWTPs affected both the prevalence and the concentration of norovirus. Mean levels of norovirus were reduced by about 2.0–1.5 log after reclamation treatments, in agreement with previous studies (Randazzo et al., 2019; Campos et al.,

Table 2

Description of the experimental setup for each trial and weather parameters recorded during the growing cycle of leafy greens irrigated with reclaimed water from the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP 1 and WWTP 2). Climatologic values are the mean ± standard deviation of the daily data over the growing cycles.

WWTP/disinfection system	Sample collection date	Leafy greens	Growing cycle (days)	Irrigation system	Water Samples	Leafy greens samples	Temperature (°C)	Radiation (W/m ²)	RH (%)
WWTP 1/chlorine	Sep–Dec 2017	Romaine	75	Furrow	45	10	13.3 ± 4.1	135.9 ± 38.8	67 ± 15
WWTP 2/UV-C	Sep–Nov 2017	Baby spinach	61	Overhead	50	5	18.2 ± 2.8	188.7 ± 37.6	67 ± 11
WWTP 2/UV-C	Dec 2017–Feb 2018	Baby spinach	56	Overhead	75	15	10.8 ± 2.9	134.4 ± 40.8	64 ± 13
WWTP 1/chlorine	Jan–March 2018	Romaine	57	Drip	100	20	10.5 ± 3.0	158.1 ± 43.0	64 ± 14
WWTP 1/chlorine	Oct–Dec 2018	Romaine	48	Furrow	55	15	11.9 ± 2.3	194.3 ± 47.4	62 ± 16
WWTP 2/UV-C	Feb–March 2019	Baby spinach	35	Overhead	75	15	12.8 ± 1.7	186.7 ± 44.5	68 ± 10
WWTP 1/chlorine	Feb–March 2019	Romaine	57	Drip	75	15	12.1 ± 3.4	148.1 ± 51.9	66 ± 16

2016). In general, a high prevalence of norovirus have been reported in raw sewage water, but in most cases, it significantly decreases after reclamation treatments, with reductions ranges between 25 and 75% (Randazzo et al., 2019; Rusiñol et al., 2020).

When monitoring norovirus in the water reuse systems a significant reduction in Noroviruses GI and GII in the WWTP and the grower's water reservoirs was observed. As described in the new European legislation (EC, 2020), reclamation facility operators can store reclaimed water after the outlet and before delivering it to the next step in the chain. This fact happened in the wastewater reuse systems examined in which, the reclaimed water was stored before the end-user. The storage of reclaimed water can contribute to the water management of the system, but it also may impact water quality. In the present study, significant reductions in noroviruses GI and GII levels were observed when water was stored in the water reservoirs near the growing field. None of the water samples tested from grower reservoirs (n = 90) were positive for norovirus (Figs. 3 and 4). Several factors might have contributed to the reductions observed, including; 1) mixing the reclaimed water with other water sources such as groundwater or surface water from a canal. In all the cases, the mixing rate was variable but always below 20%, depending on the water availability and the grower's decision; 2) the tendency of the virus to be adsorbed into the organic material present in the reservoir (Ye et al., 2016); and 3) the impact of the solar radiation on the virus reduction. Previous studies already demonstrated the efficacy of solar radiation in reducing norovirus levels, indicating that this is a feasible disinfection process (Polo et al., 2015; Rivadulla et al., 2017). Significant aridity, and high solar radiation, characterized the climatic conditions in the area where the experimental work was performed (Table 1). Based on our results, the virus die-off

during water storage could be considered an additional step in a multi-barrier approach for the overall water reuse system. These circumstances, combined with other issues such as the type of crop irrigated, irrigation method, and post-harvest processing, may help to reduce the potential safety risk linked to leafy greens irrigated with reclaimed water (FAO and WHO, 2019).

At the irrigation point, very few water samples were positive for the presence of norovirus GI (8/95) and GII (8/95). Three positive samples were detected in spray irrigation and 13 in furrow irrigation. Based on the obtained results, it is confirmed that drip irrigation systems represent a lower risk when compared to other types of irrigation systems such as furrow and spray irrigation (Figs. 3 and 4).

Several studies already reported moderate-high prevalence of noroviruses in environmental water samples from different agricultural regions and fresh produce (Tian et al., 2017; De Keuckelaere et al., 2018). In the present study, 5% (5/95) of leafy green samples collected were positive for norovirus GI, (c.a. 1 log gc/100 mL). On the other hand, none of the samples were positive for norovirus GII in line with the higher environmental stability reported for norovirus GI. Torok et al. (2019) reported a prevalence of 2.2% in noroviruses in Australian leafy greens, considering the risk of foodborne illness from norovirus associated with leafy greens as low to moderate. Similar levels were also reported for fresh Korean produce (0.5%) and environmental (2.1%) samples (Shin et al., 2019). López-Gálvez et al. (2018) reported that lettuces irrigated with water containing moderate to high levels of norovirus were negative for their presence. The present study demonstrates that irrigation water used in primary production can be contaminated with viruses but the prevalence in fresh produce seems relatively low.

Table 3

Oligonucleotide primers and probes used in this study.

Virus	Name	Primers and probe	Concentration (µM)	RT-QPCR conditions	Reference
NGI	QNIF4 (FW):	CGC TGG ATG CGN TTC CAT	10	RT: 55 °C for 60 min, preheating: 95 °C for 5 min PCR (45 cycles) 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 60 s, 65 °C for 60 s.	(ISO 15216-1:2017)
	NV1LCR (REV)	CCT TAG ACG CCATCA TCA TTT AC	10		
	NVGG1p (PROBE)	TGG ACA GGA GAY CGC RAT CT	10		
NGII	QNIF2 (FW)	ATG TTC AGR TGG ATG AGR TTC TCW GA	10	RT: 55 °C for 60 min, preheating: 95 °C for 5 min PCR (45 cycles) 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 60 s, 65 °C for 60 s.	(ISO 15216-1:2017)
	COG2R (REV)	TCG ACG CCA TCT TCA TTC ACA	10		
	QNIFS (PROBE)	AGC ACG TGG GAG GGC GAT CG	10		
HAV	HAV68 (FW)	TCA CCG CCG TTT GCC TAG	10	RT: 55 °C for 60 min, preheating: 95 °C for 5 min PCR (45 cycles) 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 60 s, 65 °C for 60 s.	(ISO 15216-1:2017)
	HAV240 (REV)	GGA GAG CCC TGG AAG AAA G	10		
	HAV150(–) (PROBE):	CCT GAA CCT GCA GGA ATT AA	10		
Mgv	Mengo 110 (FW):	GCG GGT CCT GCC GAA AGT	10	RT: 55 °C for 60 min, preheating: 95 °C for 5 min PCR (45 cycles) 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 60 s, 65 °C for 60 s.	(ISO 15216-1:2017)
	Mengo 209 (REV)	GAA GTA ACA TAT AGA CAG ACG CAC AC	10		
	Mengo 147 (PROBE)	ATC ACA TTA CTG GCC GAA GC	10		

Fig. 3. Levels of norovirus GI in the different sampling points throughout the water reuse systems from the inlet until the endpoint of irrigated leafy greens: (A) overhead, (B) drip and (C) furrow. Boxplots show median concentrations (log gc/100 mL or g) with the 25th and 75th percentile values of norovirus GI. The percentage indicates the presence of norovirus GI in each sample. Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$, according to Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test.

On the other hand, it is not possible to determine if the detected viruses are genetic material, infectious or non-infectious viruses. Previous studies attempted the discrimination between infectious and non-infectious virus using RT-qPCR combined with photoactivatable dyes (i.e. propidium monoazide, PMA and ethidiummonoazide, EMA) (Randazzo et al., 2016; López-Gálvez et al., 2018). Although these pre-treatments have the potential to be integrated in routine diagnoses to improve the interpretation of positive norovirus results obtained by RT-qPCR, further research is needed for the implementation of this methodology in raw sewage in a routine basis.

3.2. Monitoring of total coliphages in water reuse systems

Counts of total coliphages were evaluated throughout the operations steps of the water reuse systems. All water samples taken from the inlet were positive for total coliphages with median counts of 6.1 log PFU/100 mL (IQR 5.99–6.37) (Fig. 5). These values agree with previously published data on raw sewage (Chacón et al., 2020; Nappier et al., 2019; Hata et al., 2011; Levantesi et al., 2010). In general, reclamation treatments applied in the WWTPs considerably reduced the prevalence and counts of coliphages (Fig. 5). Median values of the positive samples were close to 1 log PFU/100 mL, with some outlier points around 2 log PFU/100 mL. The recently approved European regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse specifies that validation monitoring shall be performed for the most stringent reclaimed water quality class, to assess that the performance targets are complied with (EC, 2020). For total coliphages, the performance target (log₁₀ reduction) for the

validation monitoring was set at ≥ 6.0 log units. Reductions obtained at the outlet of the WWTPs were below (c.a. 5 log units) indicating that the reclamation treatments should be intensified or combined with other oxidation processes to comply with the current legislation.

Coliphages are commonly found in irrigation water (Cole et al., 2003). However, in the present study, only 11% (11/100) of the irrigation water samples were positive for the presence of total coliphages, showing very low median values of 1.0 log PFU/100 mL (IQR 0.98–1.10) (Fig. 5). Accordingly, low prevalence and low levels of coliphages were detected in leafy greens samples. Ours results agree with Perez-Mercado et al. (2018), who reported levels below 1 log PFU/g in lettuce samples irrigated with poor-quality irrigation water.

3.3. Efficacy of disinfection treatments

The different WWTPs with two reclamation treatments, chlorine and UV-C, were included in this study to evaluate the efficacy of these disinfection treatments. The WWTP 1 used chlorine, while the WWTP 2 used UV-C light. Each WWTP outlet was assayed for more than two years. Previous studies have shown that the virus concentrations in secondary treatment and chlorinated effluents were similar (Katayama et al., 2008; Francy et al., 2012). In the present study, average reductions of norovirus GI in reclaimed water treated with UV-C or chlorine were within the range of 1.5–2.0 log units (Fig. 6A). However, in the case of norovirus GII, significant differences were observed between the two reclamation treatments, even though a large variability was observed among water samples (Fig. 6B). The high efficacy of UV-C against a

Fig. 4. Levels of norovirus GII in the different sampling points throughout the water reuse system from the inlet until the endpoint of irrigated leafy greens: (A) overhead, (B) drip and (C) furrow. Boxplots show median concentrations (log gc/100 mL or g) with the 25th and 75th percentile values of norovirus GII. The percentage indicates the presence of norovirus GII in each sample. Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$, according to Tukey honest significant difference (HSD) test.

Fig. 5. Levels of total coliphages (log PFU/100 mL or g) in the different sampling points throughout the water reuse system from the inlet until the endpoint of irrigated leafy greens: (A) overhead, (B) drip and (C) furrow. Boxplots show median concentrations (log PFU/mL or g) with the 25th and 75th percentile values of total coliphages. The percentage indicates the presence of total coliphages in each sample. Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$, according to Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test.

wide range of pathogens, including chlorine-resistant viruses and protozoa, has been already demonstrated (Zholdakova et al., 2017). The efficacy of the UV disinfection system depends on the characteristics of the wastewater, the intensity of UV radiation, the exposure time to the radiation, and the reactor configuration (USEPA, 2003). However, disinfection studies performed in conventional WWTPs usually report inconclusive results on log removals of enteric viruses after reclamation treatments, due to the occurrence of non-detects with multiple reporting limits (Francy et al., 2012).

Several studies have evidenced that sewage-related microorganisms have different sensitivities to chlorination (Tree et al., 2003; Francy et al., 2012). Additionally, it has been shown that viruses in wastewater can be embedded in or associated with suspended solids, which might increase their survival against disinfection treatments (Tree et al., 2003). Therefore, relevant data to determine the efficacy of different disinfection treatments should be gathered in conventional WWTPs, mostly because data obtained in lab-scale trials cannot be extrapolated to reality. Simhon et al. (2019) enumerated noroviruses in pre- and post-disinfection effluent in five WWTPs in Ontario (Canada). In a

full-year monthly sampling, they found that chlorine and UV-C disinfection produced modest log reductions (0.5–0.8) for norovirus GI and GII. They concluded that enteric viruses were abundant in wastewater effluent following routine chlorine or UV disinfection processes that target *E. coli* metrics (Simhon et al., 2019).

3.4. Correlation between human enteric viruses and coliphages

A scatterplot represented in Supplementary File 1 shows the relationship between norovirus GI and coliphages in all water samples. No coliphages were detected in 385 samples out of 570 analyzed. Out of those, 96 samples (25%) had a norovirus GI concentration above the detection limit (0.8 log gc/100 mL). Omitting those samples with a concentration of norovirus below the detection limit (289 samples), the average concentration of norovirus in 96 samples with the absence of coliphages was 2.19 log gc/100 mL with a standard deviation of 0.64 log gc/100 mL. When norovirus GII was analyzed, 114 samples (20%) showing a norovirus concentration above the detection limit (1.2 log cg/100 mL) were negative for coliphages (Supplementary File 2). In positive samples

Fig. 6. Reduction of human enteric virus, norovirus GI (A) and norovirus GII (B) after the tertiary disinfection treatment with UV-C or chlorine. The 0 log (N/N₀) indicates no reduction of virus in water. Boxplots show median with the 25th and 75th percentile values of reduction. Boxplots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference among treatment at $P < 0.05$, according to Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test.

Fig. 7. Histogram of the norovirus GI (A) and GII (B) levels in negative samples for coliphages.

for norovirus GII and negative for coliphages, the average concentration of norovirus GII was 2.81 log gc/100 mL with a standard deviation of 0.75 log gc/100 mL. The distribution of the norovirus concentration in samples with the absence of coliphages is shown in Fig. 7A for norovirus GI and in Fig. 7B for norovirus GII. These figures illustrate that the absence of coliphages cannot be unmistakably associated with the absence of norovirus. However, in samples where the concentration of coliphages was above the quantification limit (1 log PFU/100 mL), there was correlation between coliphage concentrations and norovirus ($\rho = 0.63$ for norovirus GI, $\rho = 0.61$ for norovirus GII). This fact indicates that there is a higher likelihood of norovirus in those samples with high concentrations of coliphages (Supplementary Files 1 and 2). Meta-analyses conducted in wastewater matrices pointed out that bacteriophages, particularly somatic coliphages, are good surrogates of human enteric viruses (Chacón et al., 2020). The reason for that are their similar characteristics, the high concentrations, and low-cost methods that distinguish infectious viruses from noninfectious viruses.

If samples from different operational steps are examined together, it is difficult to establish good relationships because comparisons are not possible due to the great microbial quality. Some samples may have been exposed to disinfection treatments, while others are directly taken from the inlet of the WWTP. Many attempts have been carried out to establish a coliphage threshold approach to improve reclaimed water management. In some cases, some correlations between human enteric viruses and somatic coliphages have been found (Boehm, 2019; Chacón et al., 2020). However, more research is needed to validate the proposed threshold for its use in reclamation treatments. In general, correlations between the levels of coliphages and human enteric viruses in water have been studied, but contradictory results have been found. One reason could be that norovirus are quantified using molecular methods, which do not allow differentiation between infectious and non-infectious norovirus but genetic material. However, in the case of coliphages, the methodology allows the quantification of infectious phages. Based on the results obtained, the absence of coliphages does not mean a negative sample for norovirus.

4. Conclusions

This study shows the monitoring of human enteric viruses and coliphages in two water reuse systems from the inlet of the WWTPs to the endpoint of use. Hepatitis A virus was only detected in about 2% of the water samples, corresponding mostly to raw sewage samples. None of the leafy greens samples were positive for HAV. Reclamation treatments, including chlorine and UV-C treatments, reduced the prevalence

and concentration of norovirus in reclaimed water (c.a. 1.5–2 logs). However, the highest reductions in norovirus counts were observed in the water reservoir located close to the growing field. Cross-contamination of the reclaimed water could be possible at the irrigation point, mainly in the furrow irrigation system.

Based on the obtained results only a few samples of leafy greens taken at the growing field were positive (<5%) for norovirus. Levels of norovirus and coliphages in the irrigation water and leafy greens were very low (<1 log). These results suggested that the water from the reservoirs did not cause the contamination associated with the irrigation water. Coliphages reductions obtained at the outlet of the WWTPs (c.a. 5 log units) were below the performance target of the new regulation, which indicates that treatments should be intensified to comply with the current legislation. As in many other studies, inconclusive results on log removals of noroviruses were observed when comparing the efficacy of Chlorine and UV-C light as tertiary treatments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

All authors met to develop methods used for conducting the study. Pilar Truchado, Pedro J. Simón-Andreu and Ana Allende have designed this experiment. Pilar Truchado and Gloria Sánchez conducted the molecular lab work and data analysis. Alberto Garre conducted the statistical analysis. Ana Allende and Pilar Truchado were responsible for drafting this manuscript under the advisement of María I. Gil. All other authors read the draft and provided feedback.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appealed to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful for the financial support from ESAMUR (Project 20180705), Center for Produce Safety, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Project AGL2016-75878-R) and CSIC (Intramural 201670E056). Support provided by the Fundación Séneca (19900/GERM/15) was also appreciated. P. Truchado is holding a Ramón y Cajal contract from the Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. The technical assistance of Macarena Moreno, Jenifer Cascales, Silvia Andújar and Natalia Hernández was very much appreciated.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146837>.

References

- APHA, 1989. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*. 17th edn. American Public Health Association, Washington, D.C.
- Boehm, A.B., 2019. Risk-based water quality thresholds for coliphages in surface waters: effect of temperature and contamination aging. *Environ. Sci. Process. Impacts* 21, 2031–2041.
- Campos, C.J.A., Avant, J., Lowther, J., Till, D., Lees, D.N., 2016. Human norovirus in untreated sewage and effluents from primary, secondary and tertiary treatment processes. *Water Res.* 103, 224–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.07.045>.
- Castro-Ibáñez, I., Gil, M.I., Tudela, J.A., Ivánek, R., Allende, A., 2015. Assessment of microbial risk factors and impact of meteorological conditions during production of baby spinach in the Southeast of Spain. *Food Microbiol.* 49, 173–181.
- Chacón, L., Barrantes, K., Santamaría-Ulloa, C., Solano, M., Reyes, L., Taylor, L., Valiente, C., Symonds, E.M., Achi, R., 2020. A somatic coliphage threshold approach to improve the management of activated sludge wastewater treatment plant effluents in resource-limited regions. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 86, e00616. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00616-20>.
- Cole, D., Long, S.C., Sobsey, M.D., 2003. Evaluation of F+ RNA and DNA coliphages as source-specific indicators of fecal contamination in surface waters. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 69, 6507–6514.
- De Keuckelaere, A., Baert, L., Stals, A., Delbeke, S., Laurysen, S., Jaxsens, L., Sas, B., Uytendaele, M., 2018. Survey conducted by a consumer organization for the presence of bacterial and viral pathogens on high risk fresh produce from the Belgian market. *Acta Hort.* 1209, 459–465. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2018.1209.67>.
- EC, European Commission, 2020. Regulation (EC) no 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse. *Off. J. Eur. Union* L 177 (63), 32–55.
- Eftim, S.E., Hong, T., Soller, J., Boehm, A., Warren, I., Ichida, A., Nappier, S.P., 2017. Occurrence of norovirus in raw sewage – a systematic literature review and meta-analysis. *Water Res.* 111, 366–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.01.017>.
- FAO/WHO, 2019. *Safety and Quality of Water Used in Food Production and Processing – Meeting Report*. Microbiological Risk Assessment Series No. 33 (Rome).
- Farkas, K., McDonald, J., Malham, S., Jones, D., 2018. Two-step Concentration of Complex Water Samples for the Detection of Viruses MPs. 1, p. 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mps1030035>.
- Francy, D.S., Stelzer, E.A., Bushon, R.N., Brady, A.M., Williston, A.G., Riddell, K.R., Borchardt, M.A., Spencer, S.K., Gellner, T.M., 2012. Comparative effectiveness of membrane bioreactors, conventional secondary treatment, and chlorine and UV disinfection to remove microorganisms from municipal wastewaters. *Water Res.* 46, 4164–4178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2012.04.044>.
- Guzmán, C., Mocé-Llivina, L., Lucena, F., Jofre, J., 2008. Evaluation of *Escherichia coli* host strain CB390 for simultaneous detection of somatic and F-specific coliphages. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 74, 531–534. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01710-07>.
- Hata, A., Katayama, H., Kitajima, M., Visvanathan, C., Nol, C., Furumai, H., 2011. Validation of internal controls for extraction and amplification of nucleic acids from enteric viruses in water samples. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 77, 4336–4343. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00077-11>.
- Hedberg, C.W., Osterholm, M.T., 1993. Outbreaks of food-borne and waterborne viral gastroenteritis. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* 6, 199–210. <https://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.6.3.199>.
- ISO 10705-1. *Water Quality: Detection and Enumeration of Bacteriophages. 1. Enumeration of F-specific RNA Bacteriophages*. ISO 10705-1. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- ISO 15216-1:2017. *2017. Microbiology of the Food Chain – Horizontal Method for Determination of Hepatitis A Virus and Norovirus Using Real-Time RT-PCR – Part 1: Method for Quantification*. ISO, Geneva.
- ISO/TS 15216, 2013. *Microbiology of Food and Animal Stuffs—Horizontal Method for Detection of Hepatitis A Virus and Norovirus in Food Using Real-time RT-PCR*. International Organization for Standardization.
- Ji, M., Liu, Z., Sun, K., Li, Z., Fan, X., Li, Q., 2020. Bacteriophages in water pollution control: Advantages and limitations. *Front. Environ. Sci. Eng.* 15, 84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11783-020-1378-y>.
- Katayama, H., Haramoto, E., Oguma, K., Yamashita, H., Tajima, A., Nakajima, H., Ohgaki, S., 2008. One-year monthly quantitative survey of noroviruses, enteroviruses, and adenoviruses in wastewater collected from six plants in Japan. *Water Res.* 42, 1441e1448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.10.029>.
- Levantesi, C., La Mantia, R., Masciopinto, C., Böckelmann, U., Ayuso-Gabella, M.N., Salgot, M., Tandoi, V., Van Houtte, E., Wintgens, T., Grohmann, E., 2010. Quantification of pathogenic microorganisms and microbial indicators in three wastewater reclamation and managed aquifer recharge facilities in Europe. *Sci. Total Environ.* 408, 4923–4930.
- López-Gálvez, F., Truchado, P., Sánchez, G., Aznar, R., Gil, M.I., Allende, A., 2016. Occurrence of enteric viruses in reclaimed and surface irrigation water: relationship with microbiological and physicochemical indicators. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 121, 1180–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.13224>.
- López-Gálvez, F., Randazzo, W., Vásquez, A., Sánchez, G., Decol, L.T., Aznar, R., Gil, M.I., Allende, A., 2018. Irrigating lettuce with wastewater effluent: does disinfection with chlorine dioxide inactivate viruses? *J. Environ. Qual.* 47, 1139–1145. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2017.12.0485>.
- Mancuso, G., Lavrić, S., Toscano, A., 2020. Chapter 3: reclaimed water to face agricultural water scarcity in the Mediterranean area: an overview using sustainable development goals preliminary data. In: Verlicchi, P. (Ed.), *Advances in Chemical Pollution, Environmental Management and Protection*. 5. Academic Press, UK, pp. 113–143.
- McMinn, B.R., Ashbolt, N.J., Korajkic, A., 2017. Bacteriophages as indicators of faecal pollution and enteric virus removal. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.* 65, 11–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lam.12736>.
- Nappier, S.P., Hong, T., Ichida, A., Goldstone, A., Eftim, S.E., 2019. Occurrence of coliphage in raw wastewater and in ambient water: a meta-analysis. *Water Res.* 153, 263–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.12.058>.
- Pearce-Walker, J., Bright, K.R., Canales, R.A., Wilson, A.M., Verhougstraete, M.P., 2020. Managing leafy green safety from adenoviruses and enteroviruses in irrigation water. *Agric. Water Manag.* 240, 106272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2020.106272>.
- Perez-Mercado, L.F., Lalander, C., Joel, A., Ottoson, J., Iriarte, M., Oporto, C., Vinnerås, B., 2018. Pathogens in crop production systems irrigated with low-quality water in Bolivia. *J. Water Health* 16, 980–990.
- Polo, D., García-Fernández, I., Fernández-Ibáñez, P., Romalde, J.L., 2015. Solar water disinfection (SODIS): impact on hepatitis A virus and on a human norovirus surrogate under natural solar conditions. *Int. Microbiol.* 18, 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.2436/20.1501.01.233>.
- R Core Team, 2016. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Randazzo, W., López-Gálvez, F., Allende, A., Aznar, R., Sánchez, G., 2016. Evaluation of viability PCR performance for assessing norovirus infectivity in fresh-cut vegetables and irrigation water. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 229, 1–6.
- Randazzo, W., Piqueras, J., Evtoski, Z., Sastre, G., Sancho, R., Gonzalez, C., Sánchez, G., 2019. Interlaboratory comparative study to detect potentially infectious human enteric viruses in influent and effluent waters. *Food Environ. Virol.* 11, 350–363. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12560-019-09392-2>.
- Rivadulla, E., García-Fernández, I., Romalde, J.L., Fernández-Ibáñez, P., Polo, D., 2017. Solar radiation and photo-Fenton systems: novel applications for norovirus disinfection in water (book chapter). *Noroviruses: Outbreaks, Control and Prevention Strategies*, pp. 153–178.
- Rodríguez-Díaz, J., Querales, L., Caraballo, L., Vizzi, E., Liprandi, F., Takiff, H., Betancourt, W.Q., 2009. Detection and characterization of waterborne gastroenteritis viruses in urban sewage and sewage polluted river waters in Caracas, Venezuela. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 75, 387–394.
- Rodríguez-Manzano, J., Miagostovich, M., Hundesa, A., Clemente-Casares, P., Carratala, A., Buti, M., Jordi, R., Girones, R., 2010. Analysis of the evolution in the circulation of HAV and HEV in eastern Spain by testing urban sewage samples. *J. Water Health* 8, 346–354. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wh.2009.042>.
- Rosuñol, M., Hundesa, A., Cárdenas-Youngs, Y., Fernández-Bravo, A., Pérez-Cataluña, A., Moreno-Mesoner, L., Moreno, Y., Calvo, M., Alonso, J.L., Figueras, M.J., Araujo, R., Bofill-Mas, S., Girones, R., 2020. Microbiological contamination of conventional and reclaimed irrigation water: evaluation and management measures. *Sci. Total Environ.* 710, 136298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136298>.
- Shin, H., Park, H., Seo, D.J., Jung, S., Yeo, D., Wang, Z., Park, K.H., Choi, C., 2019. Foodborne viruses detected sporadically in the fresh produce and its production environment in South Korea. *Foodborne Pathog. Dis.* 16, 411–420. <https://doi.org/10.1089/fpd.2018.2580>.
- Shoushtarian, F., Neghaban-Azar, M., 2020. Worldwide regulations and guidelines for agricultural water reuse: a critical review. *Water* 12, 971. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12040971> 2020.
- SIAM, 2019. *SIAM and Sistema de Información Agraria de Murcia (2019)*. <http://siam.imida.es/apex/fp=101:46:4204976461560039>. (Accessed 1 July 2019).
- Simhon, A., Pileggi, V., Flemming, C.A., Bicudo, J.R., Lai, G., Manoharan, M., 2019. Enteric viruses in municipal wastewater effluent before and after disinfection with chlorine and ultraviolet light. *J. Water Health* 17, 670–682. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wh.2019.111>.
- Tian, P., Yang, D., Shan, L., Wang, D., Li, Q., Gorski, L., Lee, B.G., Quiñones, B., Cooley, M.B., 2017. Concurrent detection of human norovirus and bacterial pathogens in water samples from an agricultural region in Central California Coast. *Front. Microbiol.* 8, 1560. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01560>.
- Tombini Decol, L., López-Gálvez, F., Truchado, P., Tondo, E.C., Gil, M.I., Allende, A., 2019. Suitability of chlorine dioxide as a tertiary treatment for municipal wastewater and use of reclaimed water for overhead irrigation of baby lettuce. *Food Control* 96, 186–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.08.036>.
- Torok, V.A., Hodgson, K.R., Jolley, J., Turnbull, A., McLeod, C., 2019. Estimating risk associated with human norovirus and hepatitis A virus in fresh Australian leafy greens and berries at retail. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 309, 108327.
- Tree, J.A., Adams, M.R., Lees, D.N., 2003. Chlorination of indicator bacteria and viruses in primary sewage effluent. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 69, 2038–2043. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.69.4.2038-2043.2003>.
- Tudela, J.A., López-Gálvez, F., Allende, A., Gil, M.I., 2019. Chlorination management in commercial fresh produce processing lines. *Food Control* 106, 106760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2019.106760>.
- United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), 2003. *Wastewater Technology Fact Sheet: Disinfection for Small Systems*. EPA-832-F-03-024. Office of Water, Municipal Technology Branch, Washington, D.C. Print.
- Ye, Y., Ellenberg, R.M., Graham, K.E., Wigginton, K.R., 2016. Survivability, partitioning, and recovery of enveloped viruses in untreated municipal wastewater. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 5077–5085. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b00876>.
- Zholdakova, Z.I., Tulsakaya, E.A., Kostuchenko, S.V., Tkachev, A.A., 2017. Ultraviolet disinfection as an element of multi-barrier approach to the water treatment for the protection against chlorine-resistant pathogens. *Gigiena Sanitariya* 96, 531–535. <https://doi.org/10.18821/0016-9900-2017-96-6-531-535>.